

A STUDY ON FACTORS INFLUENCING PLUS SIZE FASHION APPAREL

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ABSTRACT

Plus-size- A particular segment of the market which was underserved for a long time is also being attracted towards fashion. This study tries to explore the Apparel Satisfaction, Non-Wear and Discard habits of plus size clothing in India. This study considers three major dimensions as: Shopping Satisfaction, Buying Satisfaction and Consuming Satisfaction. Plus-size fashion online consumers have specificities and unique motivational factors that affect their shopping preference. This study took the quantitative and qualitative approach with a sample size of 300 people to understand the needs and wants of Plus Size people in India. From this study we could understand that Plus Size people are unsatisfied in some way or the other with each of dimensions like satisfaction, style, scarcity was sometimes coupled with weight fluctuation and need for various sizes in the wardrobe causing non-wear of some apparel, in addition it is observed that few customers were holding onto their small clothing because their weights fluctuated frequently and they expected that it would fit in again one day. This study provides the designers and retailers with information which can be used as a starting point to cater to the plus-size customer segment.

KEYWORDS: Plus-Sized Clothing, Satisfaction and Dissatisfaction, Varieties & Styles

INTRODUCTION

Customer Satisfaction is the foremost factor in the utilization cycle of attire. Attire Consumption depicts the activities identified with Acquiring, Storing and Dealing with, utilizing, and disposing of clothing (Alissa, 2016). The Plus size apparel industry as we are aware goes back to the 1920s when Lane Bryant, who had solely sold maternity garments until this point, started offering size 14 to 72(Scaraboto& Fischer, 2013).A Consumer's Satisfaction with an Apparel can dictate whether they buy the apparel or not, the amount they are willing to pay for the apparel and whether they keep the apparel or not. At times any consumer may be dissatisfied with apparel, but few studies demonstrate that inside the Apparel Sizing Spectrum, Plus-size customers are the most dissatisfied customers concerning apparel satisfaction in the consumption process. Specifically, it is evidenced that plus-size individuals are dissatisfied with Apparel Fit, Apparel Style or Simple Aesthetics and also with the Apparel alternatives available. Because of increased Obesity Rates in recent years, the plus-size apparel market is considered to be a growing segment of the Indian apparel industry.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

There are a lot of studies conducted which examine the plus-size Dissatisfaction in the consumption process, whereas a little study is conducted on the relationship between Plus Size Dissatisfaction and consequent non-wearing and discarding of dissatisfied apparel. There are no studies on the Apparel Discarding patterns among consumers. In addition to that, there is a research gap on the PlusSize Consumer experience relating to the PlusSize Clothing in a formatted Survey, Questionnaire or Observation, where these forms of gathering the

data are valid but they miss out on the direct first-person story of the customer experience with respect to Apparel Satisfaction.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

This study aims to develop an understanding of the Factors surrounding Plus Size Clothing for Customer Satisfaction, more specifically, this study aims to understand how:

- Shopping satisfaction,
- Buying satisfaction, and
- Consuming satisfaction

Influences plus-size consumer's decision to Not to wear or to discard the Plus Size Apparel.

This will be achieved by examining the Plus Size people's apparel satisfaction and to find out the satisfaction causes that lead to the apparel non-wear and discard habits of plus-size people.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The literature on Apparel disposal and Apparel Non-Wear is primarily focusing on the outcomes of Plus Size Apparel disposal process. It is identified that very less is known about the reasons for which the Apparel is Discarded and also the condition of the Apparel when it is Discarded. This study aims to bridge the gap available in the Literature and it also provides relevant information on the Plus Size Apparel satisfaction which leads to the apparel non-wear and discard habits of plus-size people with the help of Google Forms comprising of a broad range of Ages. Exploring all these elements will serve several benefits for the New Born Industry and also for Academia.

Figure1: Proposed Author's Model for Plus Size Clothing

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Renoux (1973), there were different satisfaction dimensions for his theory on Retail Satisfaction which included shopping, buying and consumption system which helps in understanding and benchmarking the level of satisfaction for the consumers. His theory also provides an understanding of the impact of Apparel Satisfaction on apparel non-wear and discard habits of plus-size people. Questionnaire study done by Chowdhary and Beale (1988), clearly depicts that Fit and Sizing were the areas in which the Plus Size customers were the most dissatisfied with, in regards to Apparel

Satisfaction. The Plus-Size Women's Clothing Stores industry is characterized by a low level of market share concentration (Adam, 2001). A frequently-cited study done a few years ago by Plunkett Research, a market-research firm, found that “67% of American women were plus-size, which means a size which is equal or larger than 14”. Those figures might not have changed much, at the same time in 2016 only 18% of clothing which was sold belonged to plus-size group according to the NPD Group which is yet another research firm (Ainsworth, 2007).

“All the Designers and retailers have not conceptualized the plus-size segment as a high-risk segment and many retailers and designers like Lane Bryant, a plus-size retailer, and Prabal Garung, a designer, have done the same” Lutz (2006). The interest in the plus-size clothing market is growing due to the increasing levels of obesity in the people and also eating disorders that affect a large number of people to become obese. To support this statement a famous clothing brand “Nike” extended its “X-sized” sportswear range, shows increased interest in the Plus Size Clothing (Alba, et.al., 1997). According to Stephen Todd (2008), there is a huge shift in the body pattern of people belonging to the age group of 40 to 50, where more than 60% of people belonging to this group are considered to be obese and require Plus Size clothing. As a result, the retailers and designers have found out the intense need of the clothing in this segment. Hence we can see a whole range of Plus Size products at the shops and boutiques which were not provided earlier.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- To examine and review the existing academic literature relating to plus size fashion.
- To analyse the various dimensions of plus size clothing leading to the satisfaction of the consumers.

DATA COLLECTION

Primary data has been collected using a structured and focused questionnaire where the questionnaire was sent to 450 people of which 313 responses were received which covered various aspects of research questions. Convenient sampling technique was used to collect the data for the research. Secondary data has been collected from books, internet, literature, other relevant documents such as magazines, journals and web resources and online libraries and other sources. There are three demographic questions that were posed within the online questionnaire such as **Gender, Age Band, and Dress Size.**

DATA ANALYSIS & SOFTWARE USED

Hypotheses are made using the data and data analysis is being done using the statistical methods such as KMO measure of sampling adequacy has been conducted to identify the Communalities of the items used in the variable. ANOVA analysis, which is performed to study the Communication and service quality related specifically to the company as well as customers. Pearson Correlation analysis was conducted between motivation factor and fashion and privacy to assess the relationship between the Software used is IBM SPSS statistics 20 and excel.

KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity**Table 1: KMO and Bartlett's Test**

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.834
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3103.934
	Df	378
	Sig.	.000

Here, KMO = 0.834 which indicates that the sample is adequate and we may proceed with the further analysis of the collected data.

Table 2: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
849	26

It is observed that Cronbach's alpha from the table is 0.849, which indicates a high level of internal consistency for our scale with this specific sample.

INFERENCEAL ANALYSIS

Ho: There is no significant difference between study variables (price and privacy, fashion, selection and motivation) across occupations.

H1: There is a significant difference between study variables (price and privacy, fashion, selection and motivation) across occupations.

Table 3: ANOVA between Study Variables (Price and Privacy, Fashion, Selection and Motivation) Across Occupation

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Fashion	Between Groups	.350	1	.350	.038	.845
	Within Groups	2831.493	310	9.134		
	Total	2831.843	311			
Selection	Between Groups	.042	1	.042	.005	.942
	Within Groups	2457.638	310	7.928		
	Total	2457.679	311			
Privacy	Between Groups	31.094	1	31.094	4.023	.046
	Within Groups	2395.903	310	7.729		
	Total	2426.997	311			
Motivation	Between Groups	5.368	1	5.368	1.092	.297
	Within Groups	1524.171	310	4.917		
	Total	1529.538	311			
Price	Between Groups	46.754	1	46.754	8.688	.003
	Within Groups	1668.319	310	5.382		
	Total	1715.074	311			

One way ANOVA shows that there is an overall significance Price (F =8.688 and 0.03, $p < 0.05$), Privacy (F =4.023 and 0.046, $p < 0.05$) across occupation. Since the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative is accepted. Whereas for fashion, selection and motivation p-value is $>$ than 0.05 Thus rejecting alternative hypothesis and accept the null hypothesis (see Table 1).

Table 4: Hypothesis for the Variables with Respect to Occupation

Variables	Hypothesis	Significance	Accepted/Rejected
Fashion	H ₀	0.845	Accepted
Selection	H ₀	0.942	Accepted
Privacy	H ₀	0.046	Rejected
Motivation	H ₀	0.297	Accepted
Price	H ₀	0.003	Rejected

H₀: There is no significant difference between study variables (price, fashion, privacy, selection and motivation) across gender

H₁: There is a significant difference between study variables (price, fashion, privacy, selection and motivation) across gender

Table 5: ANOVA between Study Variables (Price, Fashion, Privacy, Selection and Motivation) Across Gender

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Fashion	Between Groups	50.084	3	16.695	1.848	.138
	Within Groups	2781.759	308	9.032		
	Total	2831.843	311			
Selection	Between Groups	72.725	3	24.242	3.131	.026
	Within Groups	2384.954	308	7.743		
	Total	2457.679	311			
Privacy	Between Groups	53.411	3	17.804	2.310	.076
	Within Groups	2373.585	308	7.706		
	Total	2426.997	311			
Motivation	Between Groups	42.623	3	14.208	2.943	.033
	Within Groups	1486.916	308	4.828		
	Total	1529.538	311			
Price	Between Groups	34.236	3	11.412	2.091	.101
	Within Groups	1680.838	308	5.457		
	Total	1715.074	311			

The One way ANOVA result the above table is that there is an overall significance (F =0.2943 and 0.33, p<0.05), Price (F =3.131 and 0.26, p<0.05), privacy F =2.310 and 0.76, p<0.10) across gender. Since the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative is accepted. Whereas for fashion, Privacy and price the p value is > than 0.05, thus reject the alternative hypothesis and accept the null hypothesis (see Table 5).

Table 6: Hypothesis for the Variables with respect to Gender

Variables	Hypothesis	Significance	Accepted/Rejected
Fashion	Ho	0.138	Accepted
Selection	Ho	0.026	Rejected
Privacy	Ho	0.076	Rejected
Motivation	Ho	0.033	Rejected
Price	Ho	0.101	Accepted

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

Table 7: Correlations between the Study Variables

		Fashion	Selection	Motivation	Price
Fashion	Pearson Correlation	1	.659**	.434**	.297**
Selection	Pearson Correlation	.659**	1	.437**	.312**
Motivation	Pearson Correlation	.434**	.437**	1	.496**
Price	Pearson Correlation	.297**	.312**	.496**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

From table 7, it is found that the result of all the variables is statistically significant at 1 percent. It is found that while buying plus size clothing, the relationship between fashion and selection is significantly correlated at 65.9%; between fashion and motivation at 43.4%; between fashion and price at 29.7%. Similarly, the correlation between selection and motivation is 43.7%; between selection and price at 31.2% and the correlation between price and motivation is at 49.6%.

FINDINGS

From the respondents profiling, it is observed that men and women are equally distributed with 50.2 percent and 49.8 percent. Majority of the respondents belong to the age group of 23-27 years followed by 18-22 years. Studying and working respondents constitute 84 percent, from this it is evident that the research is focused on consumers of generation Y.

- **Fashion and Trend-** Majority (93 percent) of respondents confirms that they buy plus-sized clothing looking at fashionable and trendy clothes in the market. Choice of colors has been a major buying factor of 85 percent of the respondents.
- **Selection-** 90 percent of the respondents' visit plus size showroom for fashionable clothing which is not available in regular stores. Majority (87 percent) of the respondents believes plus size stores can give a variety of clothes for selection. 84 percent of respondents' visit plus size stores for a good fit of clothing. 87 and 86 percent of respondents' desire to have clothing for different social occasions and seasonal clothing respectively that is comfortable and elegant.
- **Privacy-** 65 percent of the respondents are either neutral or disagree towards statement "Avoid Changing Room", 47 percent of respondents are of the opinion to take a trial in showroom whereas 52 percent of the respondents feel comfortable trying the clothes at home. 72 percent of the respondents are open to "shopping at the clothing Centre." 53 percent of the respondents' agree that they are hesitant to buy plus sized clothing as they want to avoid body shaming by others.
- **Motivational Factors-** A majority of the respondents believe Branded Clothing (75 percent), Comfort (95 percent), Fitting (91 percent), Varieties (85 percent) motivates them to buy plus size clothing.
- **Pricing-** Respondents acceptance of pricing is influenced by customization (76 percent), Quality of fabrics (93 percent), Based on Occasions (77 percent) whereas respondents (51 percent) are not willing to pay higher prices than the smaller sized clothing.
- **Satisfaction-** Significant number of respondents (50 percent) are either neutral or disagree about not being comfortable in wearing plus size readymade clothing. This opens a new segment of customers who prefer customized clothing. 60 percent of the respondents prefer customized clothing over readymade clothing. 37

percent of the respondents are neutral and 36 percent of the respondents disagree with the statement “for paying more for just plus sized clothing than the usual sizes”.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Privacy and Motivation were found to have significant difference across the occupation of the respondents. Thus, it is suggested that companies should focus on different motivational aspects. Store layout to be restructured to facilitate consumers' privacy towards the choice of clothing. Selection, privacy and motivation were found to have significant difference across gender. It is hence understood that male and female have varied choices when it comes to the selection of plus size clothing. It is observed that few customers were holding onto their small clothing because their weights fluctuated frequently and they expected that it would fit in again one day. Others could not find another apparel that replaced the one which was becoming worn out or shaded away. Under the Retail Satisfaction Dimension for the customers of Plus Size Clothing, the customer who does not have enough locations to purchase the Plus Size Fashion Apparel contribute largely to the Style Scarcity. Under the Buying Satisfaction Dimension, price of the Plus Size Apparel is negatively affecting the consumption of Plus Size Apparel and customers are feeling that the prices of Plus Size Clothing are Costlier than the Non-Plus Size Clothing. This suggests that the strategies which are used to promote Plus Size Fashion must emphasize on educating the customers regarding the purpose of the Price Differentiation.

The company should create new trends, fashion ranges and colours to be given significant importance. The stores should focus on a variety of clothes for selection for different social occasions and create multiple segmentation of seasonal clothing. Stores should encourage for trial which will increase the footfall of plus-size customers leading to a sale. Companies should come with economic apparel ranges of new fashion trends which will help to acquire new customers in the segment.

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